

CLASSIFICATION OF FEATURES OF ADDITIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MANUFACTURE OF ENGINE BUILDING PARTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7496207>

Abstract

The article discusses approaches for classifying the features of selective laser melting technology, main defects, in the organization of high-tech production of industrial gas turbine engines with an intelligent system of design and technological preparation to improve their functional characteristics.

Developed based on expert assessment, the classifier of features of the technology of selective laser melting parts of industrial gas turbine units is part of the intelligent system for integrated design and technological preparation for the production of parts of industrial gas turbine engines.

Keywords: additive manufacturing, selective laser melting, heat-resistant alloy, configuration.

Introduction

Additive technologies make it possible to produce functional parts not only with complex spatial surface geometry, but also with a functional internal structure and geometry of cavities that cannot be obtained by other traditional methods. In this case, functionality of parts is provided as a unique ratio of strength, accuracy, and weight characteristics, as well as the ability to obtain gradient properties in terms of mechanical and thermal characteristics of parts. It caused by the directed action of laser energies and the topology of sintered layers.

However, additive technologies impose a number of limitations and increased requirements for design and technological preproduction and control of technological parameters and conditions for printing parts. The quality of printing is closely related not only to the features of powder metallurgy, but also to the physical processes occurring in local and remote zones of melting (sintering) metal-powder compositions under the influence of concentrated energy sources (laser, electron beam).

The main requirements for products obtained by additive technologies are to ensure the specified quality parameters of functional products in terms of geometric accuracy, the state of the surface layer, phase composition, structure at micro-macro and mesolevels, as well as the requirements for the absence of defects in the form of non-melting of powders, residual porosity, thermal deviation.

The main limitations of additive technologies implementation are:

- lack of materials with the required characteristics and properties;
- lack of practice and qualifications in the field of design and preparation of product models for manufacturing by additive technologies;
- lack of knowledge and practice of determining the influence of technological parameters on the quality parameters of the product;

- unsatisfactory accuracy and quality: significant leashes (distortion of the shape) from the action of residual stresses, distortion of the product shape depending on the direction and orientation of the part during printing, ensuring the geometry of internal cavities and channels, high surface roughness and the complexity of its processing;

- thickness of the alloyed layer;

- limited values of mechanical properties.

Classification of features of additive technologies

The technology of selective laser melting (SLM) of domestic metal powders is one of the most accurate additive manufacturing technologies designed for products in the rocket and space industry.

One of the main limitations of additive technologies is porosity and cracks.

The pores are formed from the gas available in the building chamber and located between the particles of metal powder, which is obligated in the process of metal evaporation.

Cracks are formed due to the formation of martensite and residual stresses in the synthesized material, which is explained by the thermomechanical and metallurgical effects.

In accordance with the experience of the laboratory of additive technologies in the implementation of the technology of SLM of domestic metal powders in the manufacture of products in the energy, aviation and aerospace industries, the following types of defects are formed:

- non-compliance of roughness with the parameters of the technical specifications;

- porosity (gas, shrinkage) in the product metal;

- non-melting and discontinuities in the metal of the product;

- lack of geometric accuracy due to displacement of layers, warping, shape deformation relative to a given model;

- cracks (laminations) caused by local rupture of the material as a result of residual stresses;
- the presence of inclusions in the metal products;
- heat-stressed states.

In this work main SLM defects that occur during manufacturing process are presented and description.

1. Metal powder shape defects:

- small particles of metal powder combined into larger formations by adhesion, interparticle cohesion, setting, sintering or fusion.
- an agglomerate of two or more particles joined by diffusion sintering in the process of obtaining powders or as a result of an additive manufacturing process.
- an agglomerate of two or more particles joined by fusion in an additive manufacturing process. As a rule, the melt gets into the loading batch of material from the used powder.

2. Surface defects:

- a defect in the form of metal powder particles of fine fractions, diffusion connected with larger particles as a result of the collision of semi-liquid drops during melt spraying.
- a surface defect in the form of a recess from the chipping of foreign inclusions or the opening of a gas bubble, having an elongated or dotted shape.
- surface defect in the form of a longitudinal narrow depression or protrusion.
- delamination: a surface defect in the form of discontinuity in the metal, oriented along the direction of deformation.
- crack: A surface defect that is a break in the metal.

3. Pores:

- a discontinuity in the material of a powder particle, which is a cavity of arbitrary shape and size.

Open pore: a discontinuity in the material of a powder particle that is topologically related to the surface of the particle (having access to the surface of the particle).

Isolated (internal) pore: a discontinuity in the material of a powder particle that is topologically unrelated to the particle surface (has no outlet to the particle surface).

Gas pore: discontinuity formed by gases trapped in a drop of melt during its crystallization.

4. Incompatibility :

- nonconformity of the chemical composition: excess of the content of normalized impurities in the control sample relative to the standards and / or deviation of the main components in excess of the allowable limits specified in the regulatory or technical documentation.

- inhomogeneous composition: a defect characterized by an uneven distribution of base and alloying elements in the bulk of the material.

- fractional composition discrepancy: deviation of the particle size distribution during the incoming control of the powder, performed by the same control methods that are specified in the manufacturer's regulatory or technical documentation.

- Technological properties discrepancy: deviation of technological properties from the allowable limits specified in the regulatory or technical documentation.

Table 1 shows the types of defects in parts that occur during their SLM production, quantitative and qualitative indicators of defects and the possible causes for their formation.

Table 1

SLM defect classes in parts manufactured

SLM defect classes	Type of SLM defect	Quantitative and qualitative indicators	Possible causes for their formation
I	Material discontinuity - crack (surface, internal, through)	The size of the defect in plan. Depth and direction of the crack. The location of the crack on the part	Crystallization stresses
	Material discontinuity - shell, accumulations of large pores	The size of the defect in plan. Depth	Local non-penetration of the layer, violation of the dosage of the powder
II	Microporosity of the material (local zone or distributed throughout the volume of the part)	Share of volume V_p , %	Shrinkage processes, capture of molecules (nitrogen, argon) during synthesis
III	Increased degree of stress-strain state of the metal	Tensile strength σ_v , MPa	Residual stresses
IV	Increased surface roughness of the part	Height of profile irregularities by ten points R_z , μm	Narrow range of optimal laser synthesis parameters

Results discussion

The main sources of defects are:

- chemical-physical properties of the material (I1);
- inaccuracies and failures in the installation of additive manufacturing (I2);
- errors in creating digital geometric models (I3);
- software inaccuracies and failures (I4);
- errors in the selection of technological parameters (I5);
- printing strategy selection errors (I6);
- errors in the selection and assignment of supporting structures and heat sinks (I7);
- inaccuracies in the location of the part on the build platform (I8).

Taking into account that the same defect from Table 1 can occur for different reasons, the concept of "probability" was introduced, which is associated with the source of this defect. An expert carries out the determination of the probability. In the work, a database of defects in the technology of selective laser melting of domestic powder materials was created in the manufacture of parts for the energy, aviation and aerospace industries based on Table 2. For each class of defects, the database contains information about the source of occurrence, the probability of occurrence, and a description. Each defect from the corresponding class is assigned its own number and attribute.

Table 2

Base of defects of SLM technology

Name of defects	Identification	Source of defects occurrence	Description	Probability
Surface crack	D01	I5	Surface defect, which is a break in the material along the direction of deformation	0,3
		I1		0,8
		I3		0,7
Crack through	D02	I2	Surface defect, which is a break in the material	0,95
		I1		0,8
Sink	D03	I1	Surface defect in the form of an indentation from foreign inclusions or opening of a gas bubble	0,9
		I5		0,3
Accumulation of large pores	D04	I1	Powder particle material discontinuity associated with particle surface	0,7
		I7		0,4
		I5		0,5
Material microporosity	D05	I1	Discontinuity of the material of the powder particle, not associated with the surface of the particle (has no exit to the surface of the particle)	0,7
		I5		0,5
Increased degree of stress-strain state of the metal	D06	I3	Residual stress, shape deformation and buckling	0,9
		I5		0,5
		I7		0,6
		I8		0,6
Increased surface roughness of the part	D07	I5	Height of profile irregularities	0,8
		I6		0,7
		I1		0,3

Based on the results of assessing the quality of blanks for products made from the heat-resistant alloy by the method of selective laser melting, obtained during research, preliminary tests, it can be concluded that the characteristic defects of the SLM technology in the implementation of a complex standard technology for the additive production of parts and assemblies of the hot part of industrial gas turbine engines are the following defects:

- 1st class: surface crack;
- 3rd class: microporosity distributed throughout the entire volume of the material;
- 4th class: increased roughness.

Conclusion

The article discusses approaches to classifying the features of selective laser melting technology in the form of defects in the organization of high-tech production of industrial gas turbine engines with an intelligent

system of design and technological preparation to improve their functional characteristics.

Developed based on expert assessment, the classifier of defects in the technology of selective laser fusion of parts of industrial gas turbine units is part of the intelligent system for the integrated design and technological preparation for the production of parts for industrial gas turbine engines.

Acknowledges

The work was financially supported by the Ministry of Education and Science of Russia as part of a comprehensive project to create high-tech production on the topic: "Organization of high-tech production of industrial gas turbine engines with an intelligent system of design and technological preparation to improve functional characteristics" (Grant Agreement No. 075-11-2021-042 dated June 24, 2021).